

A Study of Clinical Correlation of Diabetic Retinopathy and Diabetic Nephropathy in Type 2 Diabetes with Laboratory Results

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Diabetes Mellitus denotes to a cluster of common metabolic disorders that segment the phenotype hyperglycemia. Type 2 Diabetic Mellitus is a diverse group of disorders considered by inconstant degrees of insulin resistance, compromised insulin secretion, and augmented hepatic glucose production.

Purpose: The purpose of study is studying clinical correlation of diabetic retinopathy and diabetic nephropathy in Type two diabetes mellitus.

Methods: We have conducted cross sectional observation study in patients attending GGH outpatient department of ophthalmology during the period May 2023 to May 2024 on hundred patients.

Results: Early detection of screening factors for retinopathy, nephropathy may prevent the progression of disease.

Conclusion: The vision loss in diabetic retinopathy can be prevented by periodic fundus examination and blood glucose levels and timely intervention. Diabetic nephropathy can be prevented by periodic checking of blood albuminuria

Keywords: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Nephropathy, Retinopathy Fundus Examination, Albuminuria.

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Introduction

Diabetes Mellitus denotes to a cluster of common metabolic disorders that segment the phenotype hyperglycemia. Type 2 Diabetic Mellitus is a diverse group of disorders considered by inconstant degrees of insulin resistance, compromised insulin secretion, and augmented hepatic glucose production.[1] Complications that occur due to diabetes can be separated into vascular and nonvascular complications. The vascular complications of Diabetic Mellitus are auxiliary subdivided into microvascular complications constituting retinopathy, nephropathy and macro vascular complications like coronary artery disease and cerebrovascular disease and peripheral arterial disease.

While coming to the Diabetic retinopathy it is valued that DIABETIC MELLITUS affects 7.2 to 11.4% of the world populace, fifty percent of who have some degree of Diabetic Retinopathy at any given point of time.[2,3] According to World Health Organization (WHO), Diabetic Retinopathy is accountable for 3 to 7% of total blindness in Asia.[4] In India, the occurrence of Diabetic Retinopathy in general populace is 3.5%.[5]

Materials and Methods

Section deals with the methodology adopted for the

current study and various steps undertaken after gathering and capturing data for investigation.

The current Cross-sectional observational study was conducted in Rangaraya Medical College, Government General Hospital, Kakinada, on a judgmental purposive sample of 100 diabetic retinopathy patients with diabetes mellitus (type 2) identified with various stages of diabetic retinopathy attended the ophthalmology department at RMC Kakinada for a period of 1 year from 01.05.23 to 01.05.24.

Inclusion Criteria

- Diabetic Retinopathy Patients from East Godavari district attending Ophthalmology OPD, Government General Hospital, Kakinada and patients referred from medicine department presenting with Diabetic Retinopathy.
- Patients willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Glomerulosclerosis
- Patients who did not come for follow-up visits

Results

Table 1: Demographic Distribution

Age Distribution(n=100)		
Age(years)	No. of cases	Percentage
21-30	05	05%
31-40	32	32%
41-50	42	42%
>50	21	21%
TOTAL	100	100%
Sex Distribution(n=100)		
Sex	No. of cases	Percentage
MALE	64	64%
FEMALE	36	36%
TOTAL	100	100%

In the current study, males were 64% compared to 36% females. 42% diabetic retinopathy cases were in the age group of 41 to 50 years compared to 32% who were in the age group of 31 to 40 years followed by 21% who were in the age group of above 50 years and the low amount of 5% cases belong to the age group of 21 to 30 years.

Table 2: Distribution of study subjects based on clinical history (n=100)

Clinical History	No. of cases	Percentage
Blurring of Vision	43	43%
Watering of Eyes	27	27%
Pedal edema	15	15%
Increased Frequency of Micturition	15	15%
Total	100	100%

43% reported blurring of the vision whereas 27% reported with watering of eyes and pedal edema and increased frequency of micturition contributed to 15% each.

Table 3: Association amongst Diabetic Retinopathy and Diabetic Nephropathy cases(n=100)

With Diabetic Nephropathy	Without Diabetic Nephropathy
62(62%)	38(38%)

62% of the diabetic retinopathy cases were having association with diabetic nephropathy cases compared to 38% retinopathy cases who were not associated with the diabetic nephropathy cases. The study population includes patients referred from nephrology ward and medicine ward.

Table 4: Duration of Diabetes in Patients with Diabetic Nephropathy and without Diabetic Nephropathy

Duration of DM	With Diabetic Nephropathy	without Diabetic Nephropathy	Total	P value
<2 years	04(6.5%)	17(44.7%)	21(21%)	P value <0.0001 Chi square=36.9524
2 -5 years	05(8.1%)	11(28.9%)	16(16%)	
6 – 10 years	25(40.3%)	07(18.4%)	32(32%)	
>10 years	28(45.2%)	03(7.9%)	31(31%)	

21% of the cases were suffering with diabetes for less than 2 years and 16% were suffering with diabetes for a duration of 2 to 5 years and 32% were diagnosed to have diabetes between 6 to 10 years compared to 31% were suffering with the diabetes for more than 10 years.

Table 5:

BMI in DR Patients with Diabetic Nephropathy and without Diabetic Nephropathy (N=100)			
BMIkg/m²	With Diabetic Nephropathy	Without Diabetic Nephropathy	P value
<18.5	02(2%)	02(2%)	P value =0.012 Chi-square=10.9177
18.5-24.9	32(32%)	31(31%)	
25-29.9	22(22%)	04(4%)	
>30	06(6%)	01(1%)	
HBA1C Levels in DR Patients with Diabetic Nephropathy and without Diabetic Nephropathy (n=100)			
HbA1c Level mmol/lit	With Diabetic Nephropathy	Without Diabetic Nephropathy	P Value
<6	10(16.1%)	18(47.3%)	P value = 0.0004 Chi-square =0.15.527
6-8	24(38.7%)	15(39.4%)	
>8	28(45.2%)	05(13.1%)	

In the current study upon comparison of BMI, among the study subjects who have association with diabetic nephropathy a majority of 51.6% cases were in the normal range of BMI whereas 35.5% were in the preobese category and 9.7% were obese and 3.2% were underweight whereas among the study subjects who were not associated with the diabetic nephropathy majority of 81.6% cases were in the normal range of BMI whereas 10.5% were in the preobese category and 2.6% were obese and 5.3% were underweight.

28% of the cases have their HbA1c levels below 6

mmol/lit whereas 39% have their HbA1c levels 6 to 8 mmol/lit compared to 33% cases whose HbA1c levels was >8 mmol/lit and among the nephropathy associated diabetic retinopathy cases 16.1% were have their HbA1c levels below 6 mmol/lit whereas 38.7% have their HbA1c levels 6 to 8 mmol/lit compared to 45.2% cases whose HbA1c levels was > 8 mmol/lit whereas among retinopathy cases who were not associated with nephropathy 47.3% had HbA1c levels below 6 mmol/lit whereas 39.4% have their HbA1c levels 6 to 8 mmol/lit compared to 13.1% cases whose HbA1c levels was >8 mmol/lit which statistically significant.

Table 6

Serum Creatinine in with Diabetic Nephropathy and without Diabetic Nephropathy (n=100)			
Serum Creatinine	With Diabetic Nephropathy	Without Diabetic Nephropathy	P value
<1mg/dl	23(37.1%)	28(73.6%)	P Value =0.00038 Chi-square=12.6204
>1mg/dl	39(62.9%)	10(26.4%)	
Blood Urea in Patients with Diabetic Nephropathy and without Diabetic Nephropathy (N=100)			
Blood urea	With diabetic nephropathy	Without diabetic nephropathy	P value
<30mg/dl	24(38.7%)	31(81.5%)	P value =0.00002 Chi-square=17.4941
>30mg/dl	38(61.3%)	07(18.5%)	

In the current study 51% of the cases have their serum creatinine levels below 1 mg/dl whereas 49% of the cases have their serum creatinine levels above mg/dl and among the nephropathy associated diabetic retinopathy cases 37.1% have their creatinine levels below 1 mg/dl compared to 62.9% of the cases who have their serum creatinine levels of > 1mg/dl whereas among the retinopathy cases who were not associated with nephropathy 73.6% have their creatinine levels below 1 mg/dl compared to 26.4% of the cases who have their serum creatinine levels of > 1mg/dl.

In the current study 55% of the cases have their blood urea levels below 30mg/dl whereas 45% of the cases have their blood urea levels above 30 mg/dl and among the nephropathy associated diabetic retinopathy cases 38.7% have their blood urea levels below 30mg/dl compared to 61.3% of the cases who have their blood urea levels of > 30mg/dl whereas among the retinopathy cases who were not associated with nephropathy 81.5% have their blood urea levels below 30mg/dl compared to 18.5% of the cases who have their blood urea levels of > 30 mg/dl.

Table 7: Albuminuria in patients with diabetic nephropathy and without Diabetic Retinopathy (N=100)

Albuminuria Status	With Diabetic Nephropathy	Without Diabetic Nephropathy	P value
No Albuminuria	10(16.1%)	30(78.9%)	P value=<0.00001 Chi-square=39.2741
Microalbuminuria	50(80.6%)	07(18.4%)	
Macroalbuminuria	02(3.2%)	01(2.6%)	

In the current study 40% of the cases have no albuminuria whereas 57% have microalbuminuria compared to 3% cases have macro albuminuria and among the nephropathy associated diabetic retinopathy cases.

Table 8:

Stages of Diabetic Retinopathy in Patients with Diabetic Nephropathy & without Diabetic Nephropathy (n=100)			
Stages of diabetic retinopathy	With diabetic nephropathy	Without diabetic nephropathy	P value
NPDR	46(74.1%)	25(65.7%)	P value = 0.60 Chi-square=0.9958
PDR	14(22.5%)	12(31.5%)	
CSME	02(3.2%)	01(2.6%)	
Severity of NPDR in Patients with Diabetic Retinopathy & without Diabetic Nephropathy (n=71)			
Severity of NPDR	With diabetic Nephropathy	Without diabetic Nephropathy	P value

Mild	29(63%)	16(64%)	P value=0.99 Chi-square= 0.012
Moderate	13(28.2%)	07(28%)	
Severe	04(8.6%)	02(8%)	
Total	46(64.79%)	25(35.21%)	

In the current study 71% of the cases have NPDR whereas 26% have PDR compared to 3% cases who have CSME and among the nephropathy associated diabetic retinopathy cases.

In the present study among the nephropathy associated diabetic retinopathy cases 63% have mild NPDR whereas 28.2 % have moderate NPDR compared to 8.6% cases who have severe NPDR whereas among retinopathy cases who were not associated with nephropathy 64% had mild NPDR whereas 28% have moderate NPDR compared to 8% cases have severe NPDR which is found to be statistically significant.

Discussion.

While coming to the Diabetic retinopathy it is valued that DIABETIC MELLITUS affects 7.2 to 11.4% of the world populace, fifty percent of who have some degree of Diabetic Retinopathy at any given point of time. [2,3] According to World Health Organization (WHO),[1] Diabetic Retinopathy is accountable for 3 to 7% of total blindness in Asia. [4] In India, the occurrence of Diabetic Retinopathy in general populace is 3.5%. [5]

In the current study majority of 42% of the cases were [6] in the age group of 41 to 50 years with a mean age of 56.8±9.5 years ranging from the age of 21 to 77 years [7,8]

Males were 64% compared to 36% females. 41% of the study subjects were in the preobese category compared to 38% who were in the normal category of BMI and 4% be underweight and 17% of the study subjects obese. Positive family history was found among 44% of the study subjects. 62% of the diabetic retinopathy cases have association with diabetic nephropathy.

Among the study subjects who have association with diabetic nephropathy a majority of 45.2% cases were suffering with diabetes for duration of more than 10 years and 51.6% cases were in the normal range of BMI whereas 35.5% were in the pre-obese category and 9.7% be obese and 3.2% be underweight.

Among the study subjects who have association with diabetic nephropathy 61.2% be hypertensives. Among the nephropathy associated diabetic retinopathy [9] cases 16.1% have their Hba1c levels below 6 mmol/lit whereas 38.7% have their Hba1c levels 6 to 8 mmol/lit compared to 45.2% cases whose Hba1c levels was >8 mmol/lit.

In the current study 51% of the cases have their serum creatinine levels below 1 mg/dl whereas 49

%of the cases have their serum creatinine levels above mg/dl.

Among the nephropathy associated diabetic retinopathy cases 38.7% have their blood urea levels below 30mg/dl compared to 61.3% of the cases who have their blood urea levels of >30mg/dl. Among the nephropathy associated diabetic retinopathy cases 50% have their EGFR levels below 90 mmol/lit whereas 45.2% have their EGFR levels 90 - 125 mmol/lit compared to 4.8% cases whose EGFR levels was >125 mmol/lit.

71% of the cases have NPDR whereas 26% have PDR compared to 3% cases who have CSME 63% have mild NPDR whereas 28.2 %have moderate NPDR compared to 8.6% cases who have severe NPDR.

Microvascular impediments like diabetic retinopathy and diabetic nephropathy are utmost vital roots of morbidity and mortality amongst type 2 diabetes mellitus cases.

In reference, diabetic retinopathy is allied with vision threatening impediments. It can be diagnosed even at the time of diagnosis of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Thus, vision loss due to diabetic retinopathy is reversible through glycemic treatment helps to alleviate the visual acuity and prevent further loss. Proteinuria [10] may also be an indicator of severe disease with extensive vascular damage. The proteinuria appears to be an vital marker of superior diagnostic and prognostic significance.

Therefore screening for early detection and identification of risk factors for nephropathy and retinopathy may prevent the progression of microvascular complications among type 2 diabetics.

Conclusion

The vision loss in diabetic retinopathy can be prevented by periodic fundus examination and blood glucose levels and timely intervention. Diabetic nephropathy can be prevented by periodic checking of blood albuminuria.

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